

A FIRST ORDER NONLINEAR THEORY FOR THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE BEAMS WITH CLOSED CROSS SECTIONS

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ABSTRACT

A theory suitable for buckling and rotor dynamics of thin-walled composite beams with closed cross sections is developed and applied. The primary merit of the theory is its relative simplicity. The moderate rotation level of geometric nonlinearity accounts physically for the first order effects of small finite deflections and section rotations on equilibrium or dynamic motion.

Exploratory buckling studies are presented for thin-walled columns under uniform compressive loading. Wall ply layups are systematically varied for two limiting classes of tailored configurations. The results suggest that buckling and buckling mode can be controlled by configuration tailoring.

Keywords: composite beams, buckling, tailoring

1. INTRODUCTION

Elastic tailoring refers to the utilization of the design flexibility of composites to achieve performance goals. The goals are usually accomplished by selecting an appropriate structural concept, fiber orientation, ply stacking sequence and a blend of materials. In aeronautical applications, emphasis has been given to tailoring deformations which influence the aerodynamics of the system (Reference 1).

An important key to the success of elastic tailoring is modeling and analysis technology. Models must be relatively simple but provide a sound description of physical behavior. Simplicity is essential as cause-effect relationships between configuration and response must be fully understood, physical mechanisms and the parameters influencing them must be clearly identified and, generally, many iterative design analysis cycles are required. Often the analysis cycles are conducted with the aid of an optimization algorithm to reach performance goals without violating constraints that would impair structural integrity.

In the present paper, the basis of a theory for elastic behavior of thin-walled composite beams with closed cross sections is presented. This theory describes the first order nonlinear geometric effects of finite deflections on beam response. This level of theory is required to study buckling and rotor blade dynamics. Exploratory applications are presented which illustrate the theory for buckling of columns under axial compression with designed-in elastic couplings.

There has been little systematic work regarding tailoring related to buckling of thin-walled columns. Exploratory work for open section columns is presented in Reference 2.

2. FOUNDATIONS OF THE THEORY

The coordinates and the notation and sign convention for the displacement components are shown in Figure 1. The strain-displacement equations are taken to be those used by Reissner in Reference 3. In terms of the present notation, these equations are

$$\epsilon_{xx} = u_{,x} + \frac{1}{2}(v_{,x}^2 + w_{,x}^2) \quad (1)$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = v_{,x} + u_{,y} \quad (2)$$

$$\gamma_{xz} = w_{,x} + u_{,z} \quad (3)$$

As we seek first order nonlinear effects, we assume that the form of the displacement field from linear theory persists into the nonlinear range. This provides the following results:

$$u = U + y\beta_y + z\beta_z + u_1 \quad (4)$$

$$v = V - (z - z_s)\phi \quad (5)$$

$$w = W + (y - y_s)\phi \quad (6)$$

The functions U , V and W depend on the axial spanwise coordinate x only; they represent displacement components of the beam axis. The beam axis is the principal bending axis. The functions β_y , β_z and ϕ depend only on x as well; they are section rotations. The coordinates (y_s, z_s) correspond to the section shear center location relative to the x -axis. The displacement contribution u_1 corresponds to section warping effects (Reference 4), which we neglect here. Thus, our theory provides global information of the St. Venant-type where warping is free to occur.

The information in Equations 1 - 6 serves as the basis for the theory. A complete development can be created using the Principle of Virtual Work or Minimum Potential Energy. This is presented for the linear, small deflection case in Reference 4.

3. APPLICATIONS TO COMPRESSIVE BUCKLING

Tailored response utilizing elastic coupling mechanisms for thin-walled tubular beams is achieved by skewing angle plies with respect to the beam axis. Two limiting archetype configurations are shown in Figures 2 and 3. The circumferentially uniform stiffness (CUS) configuration produces extension-twist coupling with bending-transverse shear as a parasitic coupling mechanism (Reference 5). The other configuration, circumferentially asymmetric stiffness (CAS), produces bending-twist coupling with extension-transverse shear as a parasitic coupling mechanism (Reference 5). The angle θ in Figures 2 and 3 denotes the dominant off-axis angle ply orientation in the upper and lower surface wall configurations. These limiting forms are interesting because they isolate the two primary independent coupling mechanisms of extension-twist and bending-twist.

Our studies of tailored wings (Reference 6) have shown the utility of the simple cross section model shown in Figure 4. This model is adopted here. We call it the "Ideal Tailored Box Model." The upper and lower covers are load bearing, while the webs are assumed to be nonstructural. The role of the webs is to preserve the closed cell load path in torsion and maintain the geometry of the section (infinite transverse shear stiffness) while not contributing to the extensional, bending and torsional stiffnesses of the beam. Mean or averaged stiffness properties are considered uniform across the section width. Closed form expressions for all the stiffnesses permit rapid assessment of design changes and facilitate understanding of the cause-effect relationships between configuration and structural response.

Two exploratory investigations on buckling of columns under uniaxial compression have been undertaken as examples of the use of the theory. All columns are considered to have covers of four plies of AS4/3501-6 graphite-epoxy unidirectional tape with a nominal thickness of 0.140 mm (0.0055 in.) per ply. The structural chord, C_s , is taken to be 25.4 mm (1.0 in.) and the section depth, H , is 12.7 mm (0.5 in.). These dimensions would correspond to small scale models.

The first columns considered are of CAS construction. Without elastic coupling, there are three possible uncoupled buckling modes -- two Euler-type bending modes and a twisting mode. With CAS elastic coupling, there is an Euler-type bending mode about the axis normal to the covers and coupled bending-twist modes about the axis parallel to the covers. Two aspects have been explored. The first is the effect of ply layup. Five wall configurations have been considered. They are A: $[0_4]$, B: $[0_3, 45]$, C: $[0_2, 45_2]$, D: $[0, 45_3]$ and E: $[45_4]$.

For columns with a length of 40.6 cm (16.0 in.), the effect of ply layup on buckling is presented in Figure 5 for CAS construction. The coupled bending-twisting buckling mode is critical. A limit allowable axial strain of 4500 microstrain has been imposed and denoted "material failure."

In Figure 6, CAS configuration C buckling strains are plotted for various column lengths up to 600 mm. For lengths below about 300 mm, material failure is critical, and the column may be said to be "short." For longer columns, bending-twisting buckling is critical.

A similar set of studies has been conducted for CUS construction. For this type of configuration, the buckling modes -- two Euler bending and one twisting -- remain uncoupled. The effect of elastic coupling stiffnesses is to reduce the effective overall stiffnesses. The effect of ply layup for columns of length 40.6 cm (16.0 in.) is presented in Figure 7. Euler buckling about the y-axis is critical. The twisting buckling strain is so high that it is off the scale of the figure.

In Figure 8, the effect of length on buckling load is presented for CUS Configuration C. The same buckling mode is critical, and lengths below 300 mm are strain limit critical.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The foundations of a first order nonlinear theory suitable for buckling and rotor dynamics of thin-walled composite beams with closed cross sections have been presented. The primary merit of the theory is its relative simplicity. Exploratory studies of buckling under uniform compression of two limiting structural configurations have been given as examples of the theory's application. The results indicate that the buckling process can be passively controlled by configuration tailoring.

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FIGURE 1. Closed cell thin walled beam model

FIGURE 2. CUS construction

FIGURE 3. CAS construction

FIGURE 4. Ideal tailored box model

FIGURE 5. Critical strain for CAS designs

FIGURE 6. Critical strain vs. length for CAS design

FIGURE 7. Critical strain for CUS designs

FIGURE 8. Critical strain vs. length for CUS design